

PERCEIVED IMPACT OF COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING PROGRAMS AND ACTIVITIES: A BASIS FOR PROGRAM ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the perceived impact of Community Health Nursing (CHN) programs and activities conducted by volunteer student nurses and faculty members from the Bachelor of Science in Nursing Program at Holy Name University in Barangay Catarman, Daus. It aimed to elucidate participants' profiles, perceptions of CHN initiatives, potential variations based on demographic attributes, and suggested improvements based on findings. The research uncovered insightful patterns within respondents' demographic profiles, spanning age, gender, educational background, family income, family structure, and family headship. Furthermore, it scrutinized the perceived impacts of CHN endeavors, highlighting their effectiveness in disseminating health information, delivering primary health care services, and implementing essential nursing procedures. Despite some demographic-based discrepancies, the study identified overarching similarities in participants' perceptions of CHN initiatives. Conclusions underscored the significant positive influence of CHN programs on personal well-being and health status. Recommendations included tailored health education efforts, streamlined clinic management services, bolstered nursing procedures, diversified health promotion strategies, customized home visit services, consideration of socioeconomic factors, and sustained program evaluation. Implementing these recommendations promised to amplify the efficacy and reach of CHN initiatives, ultimately fostering improved health outcomes and elevated community well-being.

Keywords: *Community Health Nursing (CHN), Demographic Attributes, Health Information Dissemination, Perceived Impact, Primary Health Care Services, Program Evaluation*

INTRODUCTION

Community Health Nursing (CHN) holds significant importance in promoting the health and welfare of individuals, families, and communities. By incorporating nursing principles with public health strategies, CHN effectively addresses individual and population-based health needs (Mengistu & Misganaw, 2006). Through a steadfast commitment to prioritizing health promotion and disease prevention efforts, CHN empowers communities to adopt healthy practices and mitigate the onset of illnesses (Maglaya et al., 1987). Grounded in the community context, CHN emphasizes collaboration and engagement to tailor interventions in response to local health challenges and disparities (Castro, 2012). Furthermore, by emphasizing hands-on experiences, CHN education equips future nurses with the necessary skills to assess, plan, implement, and evaluate community health initiatives. Notably, CHN plays a pivotal role in the Philippines, addressing health needs and focusing on population-based care and partnerships (Brookes, K., et al. 2004). As per Clark's definition (2008), community health encompasses a fusion of nursing expertise and practice intertwined with the principles and methodologies of public health. It operates through a structured application of the nursing process and complementary approaches to foster health promotion and disease prevention within various population groups. This definition underscores the collaborative nature of community health endeavors, emphasizing the integration of diverse disciplines and methodologies to effectively address the multifaceted health needs of communities. Community health nurses collaborate with individuals, families, and groups to address specific health needs and maintain population health (Assessment Technologies Institute, 2010).

As community health nursing responds to the unique needs, health problems, cultural practices, and resources of the community, it serves as a profession capable of addressing diverse demands within a transitioning healthcare system. The evolving healthcare landscape requires community health nurses to possess varied capabilities to meet the complex healthcare demands of communities. Community health nursing promotes health and prevents diseases, disabilities, and premature death within populations. It provides opportunities for nurses to develop partnership skills with community stakeholders, enhancing communication and leadership capabilities while fostering creativity in problem-solving. As emphasized by the American Nursing Association (ANA), community health nursing emphasizes promoting and protecting the health of populations alongside promoting self-care among individuals and families (Matthews, J. 2012).

In this evolving landscape, community health nurses continue to care for individuals and families, particularly those at high risk or with communicable diseases. Community health nursing involves identifying high-risk groups within communities and developing policies and interventions to ensure accessible services for all population

groups. This study aimed to investigate the perceived impact of CHN programs and activities to provide valuable insights to strengthen these initiatives to benefit communities. By doing so, it sought to pave the way for evidence-based strategies that could enhance their effectiveness and ultimately contribute to improved community health outcomes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the perceived impact of Community Health Nursing programs and activities conducted by the volunteer student-nurses and the faculty of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing Program of Holy Name University in Barangay Catarman, Dausi.

Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the participants' profile in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 educational background;
 - 1.4 family income;
 - 1.5 family structure; and
 - 1.6 family head?
2. What are the participants' perceived impact of CHN programs and activities?
3. Is there a significant difference in the participants' perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities when grouped according to their demographic profile?
4. What enhancement program can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This section of the study presented the research design, research environment, participants, instruments, and procedures that were used to determine the perceived impact of the different community health nursing programs and activities implemented in Catarman, Dausi, Bohol by the Holy Name University nursing students.

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive survey method and a self-designed questionnaire as the principal tool for data collection. Employing a descriptive research design, the study aimed to portray the characteristics of a particular situation as observed at the time of the investigation and to delve into the underlying causes of specific phenomena. Central to this study was exploring the perceived impact of Community Health Nursing (CHN) programs and activities. The respondents were selected based on their participation in the various CHN programs and activities. They received proper briefing and instructions before directly answering the questions posed by the researchers.

Research Environment

This study was conducted in Dausis, Bohol, particularly in Barangay Catarman. Dausis is one of the two towns on Panglao island, just three kilometers from the City of Tagbilaran. It is one of the oldest municipalities of Bohol, located in the southwestern part of the province, with a land area of 4,524.28 hectares and a population of 36,525. Its topography is rocky but generally flat, with mountain ranges in the southeastern part. Dausis comprises twelve barangays, with Catarman being one of them. Barangay Catarman is positioned two kilometers from Poblacion, Dausis, with an estimated population of 4,152 residents. This area served as the location for the Community Health Nursing practice of nursing students from Holy Name University, College of Nursing, from 2003 to 2006. While some barangays have developed modern urban structures, others have retained a rural character, especially those in outlying areas.

Research Participants

The target respondents of this study were the residents of Catarman selected through purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique wherein the researcher consciously selects the subjects, typically targeting a specific group of respondents who have participated in various CHN programs and activities.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a self-made questionnaire as its primary research instrument, consisting of two parts. The first part focused on the respondents' demographic profile, while the second part delved into the respondents' perceptions of the impact of the CHN programs and activities. To gather the necessary data, respondents were asked about the impact of the community health programs and activities conducted. The response options provided were as follows: 4 – Greatest impact; 3 – Great impact; 2 – Lesser impact; and 1 – No impact. To establish the range of categories for responses, the highest response of 4 was subtracted from the lowest response of 1, resulting in a difference of 3. This difference was then divided by 4, representing the standard number of classes. The quotient of 0.75 was utilized to determine the interval for each response. Based on this calculation, the range of categories and their corresponding qualitative descriptions were constructed and presented below.

Qualitative Description	Range of Categories
Greatest Impact	4.0 – 3.26
Great Impact	3.25 – 2.51
Less Impact	2.50 – 1.76
No Impact	1.75 – 1.0

Research Procedure

Gathering of data. Before conducting one-on-one interviews with the respondents, the researchers sent a letter to the Mayor of Dauis, Bohol, through the Barangay Captain of Catarman, requesting permission and approval to conduct the study. Upon receiving approval, the researchers commenced the survey. To ensure access to desired data and information, permission was also sought from the Barangay Captain of Catarman, Dauis, Bohol, facilitated through a formal letter. Once approved, the questionnaires were prepared for distribution. To facilitate understanding, the questionnaires were translated. After distribution, the completed questionnaires were collected immediately, and the gathered data were subjected to statistical analysis. Data collection was also facilitated through interviews, allowing for ease and speed in gathering information. Respondents were given the freedom of choice and expression through the various items and responses in the research instrument, thereby limiting the researchers' control over respondents' perceptions. Upon completion of the interviews, the collected data underwent statistical treatment.

Treatment of Data. After the data was gathered, they were collated and tabulated. Thorough frequency counting was conducted to obtain a concise response for each question. The responses were summed up, and the equivalent percentage was derived by dividing the number of responses for each item by the total number of respondents.

The following formula was employed in the statistical treatment of the data:
Simple Percentage:

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

P = percentage
f = frequency
N = Number of cases

Weighted Mean

$$WM = \frac{\sum wx}{\sum w}$$

Where:

WM = weighted mean
w = the weight for each data point
x = the value of each data point

In determining the significant difference on the perceived impact of the CHN programs and activities based on the respondents' demographic profile, the Two Way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was used in applying the formula:

$$SS_{Total} = \sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}$$

$$SS_{Between} = \frac{(\sum X_1)^2}{n_1} + \frac{(\sum X_2)^2}{n_2} + \dots + \frac{(\sum X_{ac})^2}{n_{ac}} - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}$$

$$SS_{Within} = SS_{Total} - SS_{Between}$$

$$SS_A = \sum \frac{(\sum \text{for each row})^2}{n \text{ for each row}} - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}$$

$$SS_C = \sum \frac{(\sum \text{for each column})^2}{n \text{ for each column}} - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}$$

$$SS_{AC} = SS_{Between} - SS_A - SS_C$$

For determining the perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities:

Range	Qualitative Description
3.26 – 4.00	- Greatest Impact
2.51 – 3.25	- Great Impact
1.76 – 2.50	- Lesser Impact
1.0– 1.75	- No Impact

RESULTS

The first part presents the demographic profile of the clients as stratified into age, gender, educational background, family income, type of family structure, and family head. The demographic profile of the clients is a vital factor in getting the client's perception of the impact of the different CHN programs and activities rendered by the student nurses and clinical instructors because perception differs in every individual. Part II discusses the perceived impact of Community Health Nursing programs and activities. The options for their responses are 4 – Greatest impact, 3 – Great impact, 2 – Lesser impact, and 1 – No impact.

Table 1
Respondents' Profile in terms of Age

Ages	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20-32	10	5.7
33-44	53	30.5
45-56	52	29.9
57-68	38	21.8
69-82	21	12.1
Total	174	100.0

Table 1 shows that most respondents are between 33 and 44 years of age, comprising 30.5 percent or 53 respondents. It was closely followed by age groups between 45 – 56 years old, with a percentage of 29.9 percent. The lowest number of respondents is between 20 and 32 years old, with a corresponding percentage of 5.7 percent.

Table 2
Respondents' Profile in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
female	129	74.1
male	45	25.9
Total	174	100.0

Table 2 shows the gender profile of the respondents. The females comprise 74.1 percent of the total 129 respondents, while the male respondents comprise 25.9 percent, with a total number of 45 out of the total number of respondents, which is approximately 174.

Table 3
Respondents' Profile in terms of Educational Background

Educational Background	Frequency	Percentage (%)
College graduate	16	9.2
College level	9	5.2
High school graduate	33	19.0
High school level	51	29.3
Elementary graduate	50	28.7
Elementary level	15	8.6
Total	174	100.0

Table 3 shows an overview of the educational background of the respondents, revealing significant trends. Most respondents had attained a high school education, accounting for 51 individuals, constituting 29.3 percent of the sample. Following closely were respondents who had completed elementary education, 50 individuals and representing 28.7 percent. Conversely, the smallest proportion of respondents had reached the college level, comprising only 9 individuals, or 5.2 percent of the sample. Higher levels of education have been associated with improved health outcomes, as individuals with more education tend to have better health literacy and are more adept at managing their health concerns compared to those with lower educational attainment. Poor educational status often correlates with underutilizing healthcare services and increased avoidable risk factors.

Table 4
Respondents' Profile in terms of Family Income

Family Income	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 2,500	67	38.5
2,500-5,000	70	40.2
5,000-7,500	19	10.9
7,500-10,000	9	5.2
10,000 above	9	5.2
Total	174	100.0

Table 4 provides insights into the respondents' family income profiles. It reveals that a significant majority of respondents reported an income falling within the range of 2,500 to 5,000 pesos, comprising 40.2 percent of the sample, with a total of 70 individuals. Conversely, the smallest subset of respondents, totaling 9 individuals and representing 5.2 percent, belonged to two higher income brackets: 7,500 to 10,000 pesos and above 10,000 pesos.

Table 5
Respondents' Profile in terms of Family Structure

Family Structure	Frequency	Percent
Nuclear	173	99.4
Patriarchal	1	0.6
Total	174	100.0

Table 5 shows the respondents' profile in terms of family structure. It showed that most respondents had a nuclear family structure, with 173 out of the 174 respondents with a corresponding percentage of 99.4 percent. At the same time, only one respondent, with a percentage of 0.6 percent, had a patriarchal family structure.

Table 6
Respondents' Profile in terms of Family Head

Family Head	Frequency	Percent
Father	160	92.0
Mother	8	4.6
Child	2	1.1
Grandparents	4	2.3
Total	174	100.0

The respondents' profile in terms of family head is shown in Table 6. It showed that most respondents considered the father the dominant family head, with a total number of 160 respondents or a corresponding percentage of 92 percent. While the least number of respondents consider the child as their dominant family head, with a total number of 2 respondents with a corresponding percentage of 1.1 percent. Demographic information is essential to comprehending the population's characteristics of the population that expose them to specific health conditions.

Table 7
Perceived Impact of the Community Health Nursing Programs and Activities

Health information dissemination to clients on:	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1 The benefits of proper nutrition and diet	3.22	Great Impact
2 Creation of Health Action Committee facilitated the community in the implementation of the CHN programs and activities.	3.21	Great Impact
3 Health teachings, I became informed of the relevance of disease prevention.	3.25	Great Impact
4 Taking medication in its full course is necessary to prevent the risk of resistance.	3.03	Great Impact

5.1 Basic sanitation information.	3.22	Great Impact
5.2 Dengue fever prevention	3.31	Greatest Impact
5.3 Common illnesses related to poor environmental sanitation.	3.24	Great Impact
6.1 Knowledge on the health teachings to the mothers and barangay health workers on Food Technology and Appropriate Technology (Approtech)	3.12	Great Impact
6.2 Health teachings to the mothers and barangay health workers on hygiene and sanitation.	3.23	Great Impact
Basic Health Care Services provision for the purpose of disease prevention, illness detection and health maintenance.		
1 Feeding Program of undernourished school-aged children	3.22	Great Impact
2 Case Finding, common health problems were identified and prompt treatment were employed.	3.15	Great Impact
3 Medical Mission conducted to the residents	3.18	Great Impact
4.1 Home visits led to the development of good relationships.	3.20	Great Impact
4.2 Home visits led to identification of health problems.	3.20	Great Impact
4.3 Home visits led to implementation of appropriate interventions.	3.21	Great Impact
5 Clinic management helped the residents acquire easy access to health care services without a cost.	3.24	Great Impact
6 Health teaching and feeding programs were undertaken during school nursing activities.	3.16	Great Impact
Basic Nursing Procedures implemented by the student nurses such as:		
1 Blood pressure taking and monitoring for susceptible clients.	3.18	Great Impact
2 In-depth interview on the family's over-all health status (family assessment) to identify vulnerable and high risk groups prone to illnesses and disabilities.	3.16	Great Impact
3 Physical Examination to detect any abnormalities.	3.17	Great Impact
4 Benedict's Test to determine presence of disease condition.	3.20	Great Impact
5 Wound care management to treat any types of impaired skin integrity.	3.20	Great Impact
Other programs and activities		
1 Outreach activities to deliver services to serve population groups.	3.18	Great Impact
2 Uses of common Herbal plants in treating common health problems as well as how to prepare them.	3.15	Great Impact
3 Herbal garden gives us easy access to herbal plants.	3.21	Great Impact
4 I enjoyed the sports activity initiated as it promotes physical well-being and socialization.	3.22	Great Impact
Overall	3.19	Great Impact

Table 7 shows the Perceived Impact of the Community Health Nursing Programs and Activities. It further revealed that the highest impact on the CHN programs and activities is on health information dissemination on Dengue fever prevention, with a weighted mean of 3.31 with a qualitative description of "greatest impact." The least impact

on health information dissemination is taking medication during its entire course. It is necessary to prevent the risk of resistance with a weighted mean of 3.03 and a qualitative description of "great impact."

On basic health care services provision for disease prevention, illness detection, and health maintenance, it showed that the highest perceived impact on these CHN programs and activities is on Clinic management, which helped the residents acquire easy access to health care services without a cost with a weighted mean of 3.24 with a corresponding qualitative description of "great impact." While the least impact on these categories is on case finding in

which common health problems were identified, and prompt treatment was employed with a weighted mean of 3.15 with a qualitative description of "great impact."

On the basic nursing procedures implemented by the student nurse, the highest impact as perceived by the respondents on the implemented CHN programs and activities is on Benedict's test to determine the presence of disease condition and on wound care management for treatment of any types of impaired skin integrity with a weighted mean of 3.20 and with a qualitative description of "great impact." While the least impact is on the in-depth interview on the family's overall health status, with a weighted mean of 3.16 with a qualitative description of "great impact."

Regarding other programs and activities, the highest perceived impact on these categories is on the sports activity that promotes physical well-being and socialization, with a weighted mean of 3.22 with a qualitative description of "great impact." The least impact on the respondents in these categories is the use of common herbal plants in treating common health problems and how to prepare them, with a weighted mean of 3.16 and a qualitative description of "great impact."

Public health programs operate with a philosophy of prevention and assistance to clients to achieve and maintain the highest level of health and wellness possible for the individual. Public Health Nurses (PHNs) develop, facilitate, implement, and modify health promotion activities based on clients' needs (Practice North, n.d.). This approach highlights the proactive stance of public health programs in addressing health concerns and promoting optimal health outcomes for individuals within communities.

Health education is pivotal in disease control, particularly combating diseases like Dengue. It is crucial for community members to comprehend the mechanisms of infection and to be aware of key behaviors or activities that need addressing to prevent transmission, reduce the severity of the disease, and prevent fatalities. Community involvement is indispensable in preventing and controlling Dengue, emphasizing the collaborative effort needed to combat this health threat.

Table 8
The Significant Difference on the Perceived Impact on the CHN Programs & Activities when Grouped according to Age

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
ImpactCHN Programs * Age	Between Groups (Combined)	1308.447	4	327.112	2.254	0.065	Accept H ₀ (Insignificant)
	Within Groups	24528.409	169	145.139			
	Total	25836.856	173				

The perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities, when grouped according to the respondents' age, is shown in Table 8. The ANOVA computations reveal no significant difference in the perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities when classified according to their ages, $F(4,169) = 2.254$, $p = 0.065$. The computed p-value was lower than the set alpha 0.05 under the two-tailed test. When grouped according to the respondents' ages, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the perceived impact of the CHN programs and activities was therefore accepted. This means that the results showed 95 % confidence that no difference existed in the different brackets of ages of the respondents as to their perceived impact of CHN programs and activities.

Table 9
The Significant Difference on the Perceived Impact on the CHN Programs & Activities when Grouped according to Gender

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
ImpactCHN Programs * Gender	Between Groups (Combined)	82.994	2	41.497	0.276	0.760	Accept H ₀ (Insignificant)
	Within Groups	25753.863	171	150.607			
	Total	25836.856	173				

Table 9 shows the significant difference in the perceived impact of the CHN programs and activities when grouped according to gender. The respondents' perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities, when classified according to gender, reveals no significant difference, $F(2,171) = 0.276$, $p = 0.760$. For the respondents' gender, the male and female perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities does not vary or is the same. This similarity in the perceptions of males and females concerning the CHN programs and activities might be attributed to the fact that the programs and activities provided by the CHN apply to both males and females. With this result, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities, when grouped according to the respondents' gender, was therefore accepted.

Table 10
The Significant Difference on the Perceived Impact on the CHN Programs & Activities when Grouped according to Educational Background

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
ImpactCHN Programs * Educational Background	Between Groups (Combined)	1490.928	5	298.186	2.058	0.073	Accept H ₀ (Insignificant)
	Within Groups	24345.929	168	144.916			
	Total	25836.856	173				

Table 10 shows the significant difference in the perceived impact of the CHN programs & activities when grouped according to their educational background. The ANOVA calculations revealed no significant difference between the respondents' perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities when grouped according to their educational background, $F(5,168) = 2.058$, $p = 0.073$. This means respondents with different academic backgrounds have a similar perceived impact on CHN programs and activities.

Table 11
The Significant Difference on the Perceived Impact on the CHN Programs & Activities when Grouped according to Family Income

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Impact CHN Programs * Income	Between Groups (Combined)	1497.151	4	374.288	2.599	0.038	Reject H ₀ (Significant)
	Within Groups	24339.705	169	144.022			
	Total	25836.856	173				

As reflected in Table 11, the ANOVA computations reveal a significant difference in the perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities when grouped according to their family income, $F(4,169) = 2.599$, $p = 0.038$. This means that the perceived impact of the respondents with a higher income compared to the lower ones is contradictory with each other. The obtained value indicates that the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities classified according to their income was therefore rejected. This obviously indicates that the result displayed at least 95 % assurance that difference existed in those respondents with different incomes.

Table 12
The Significant Difference on the Perceived Impact on the CHN Programs & Activities when Grouped according to Family Structure

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Impact CHN Programs * Family Structure	Between Groups (Combined)	401.157	1	401.157	2.713	0.101	Accept H ₀ (Insignificant)
	Within Groups	25435.699	172	147.882			
	Total	25836.856	173				

The perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities, when grouped according to the respondents' family structure, is shown in Table 12. The ANOVA computations reveal that no significant difference existed in the perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities when classified as to their family structure, $F = 2.713$, $p = 0.101$. The computed p-value was lower than the set alpha 0.05 under the two-tailed test. Therefore, when grouped according to the respondents' family structure, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the perceived impact of the CHN programs and activities was accepted. This means that the results showed 95 % confidence that no difference existed in the family structure of the respondents as to their perceived impact of CHN programs and activities.

Table 13
The Significant Difference on the Perceived Impact on the CHN Programs & Activities when Grouped according to Family Head

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Impact CHN Programs * Family Head	Between Groups (Combined)	815.006	3	271.669	1.846	0.141	Accept H ₀ (Insignificant)
	Within Groups	25021.850	170	147.187			
	Total	25836.856	173				

Table 13 shows the significant difference in the perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities when grouped according to family head. When classified according to family head, the respondents' perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities reveals no significant difference, $F = 1.846$, $p = 0.141$. The perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities does not vary or is the same when they are grouped according to the family head. This similarity in the respondents' perceptions concerning the CHN programs and activities might be attributed to the fact that whatever the programs and activities provided by the CHN applies to whoever is the family head of the respondents. With this result, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities was therefore accepted when grouped according to the respondents' family head.

Findings

Based on the data being generated, the following major findings were arrived at:

1. Respondents' Demographic Profile

Age. Most of the respondents belong to the age group between 33 – 44 years of age, with a total of 53 respondents comprising 30.5 percent. The lowest number of respondents is between 20 – and 32 years old, with a corresponding percentage of 5.7 percent.

Gender. The females comprise 74.1 percent of the total 129 respondents, while the male respondents comprise 25.9 percent, with a total number of 45 out of the total number of respondents, which is approximately 174.

Educational Background. It showed that most respondents had attained the high school level, with a total number of 51 and a percentage of 29.3 percent. The lowest number of respondents is those who reached the college level, with 9 respondents and a percentage of 5.2 percent.

Family Income. Most respondents have an income of 2,500 – 5,000 pesos, with a percentage of 40.2 percent and a total number of 70 respondents. On the other hand, the least number of respondents, comprising a total number of 9 respondents and with a corresponding percentage of 5.2 percent, belong to two family income brackets: are the income bracket of 7,500 – 10,000 pesos and those whose income is above 10,000 pesos.

Family Structure. Most of the respondents had a nuclear family structure, with a total of 173 respondents out of the total 174 respondents with a corresponding percentage of 99.4 percent. While only one respondent with a percentage of 0.6 percent had a patriarchal family structure.

Family Head. Most respondents considered the father as the dominant family head, with a total number of 160 respondents or a corresponding percentage of 92 percent. While the least number of respondents consider the child as their dominant family head, with a total number of 2 respondents with a corresponding percentage of 1.1 percent.

2. Perceived Impact of Community Health Nursing Programs and Activities

It showed that the highest impact of the CHN programs and activities is on health information dissemination on Dengue fever prevention, with a weighted mean of 3.31 with a qualitative description of "greatest impact." While the least impact on health information dissemination is on taking medication on its full course, which is necessary to prevent the risk of resistance with a weighted mean of 3.03 with a qualitative description of "great impact."

On basic health care services provision for disease prevention, illness detection, and health maintenance, it showed that the highest perceived impact on these CHN programs and activities is on Clinic management, which helped the residents acquire easy access to health care services without a cost with a weighted mean of 3.24 with a corresponding qualitative description of "great impact." While the least impact on these categories is on case finding in

which common health problems were identified, and prompt treatment was employed with a weighted mean of 3.15 with a qualitative description of "great impact".

On the basic nursing procedures implemented by the student nurse, the highest impact as perceived by the respondents on the implemented CHN programs and activities is on Benedict's test to determine the presence of disease condition and on wound care management for treatment of any types of impaired skin integrity with a weighted mean of 3.20 and with a qualitative description of "great impact." While the least impact is on the in-depth interview on the family's overall health status, with a weighted mean of 3.16 with a qualitative description of "great impact."

Regarding other programs and activities, the highest perceived impact on these categories is on sports activities that promote physical well-being and socialization, with a weighted mean of 3.22 and a qualitative description of "great impact." The least impact on the respondents in these categories is the use of common herbal plants in treating common health problems and how to prepare them, with a weighted mean of 3.16 and a qualitative description of "great impact." Public health programs adhere to a philosophy focused on prevention and client assistance, aiming to attain and sustain the utmost level of health and wellness achievable for everyone. Public Health Nurses (PHNs) are tasked with developing, facilitating, implementing, and adjusting health promotion activities according to clients' needs (Practice North, n.d.). This approach underscores the proactive stance of public health programs in addressing health concerns and promoting optimal health outcomes for individuals within communities.

Health education within Community Health Nursing (CHN) promotes health and prevents diseases by disseminating accurate information and educating individuals. Through community collaborative efforts, Public Health Nurses (PHNs) educate individuals about health issues, enhance community health and safety, and improve access to healthcare services. They provide reliable and practical information to empower individuals to protect their health and well-being. The primary goal is to present health information understandably, enabling individuals to take control of their health.

Moreover, health education is indispensable in controlling diseases such as Dengue, as it ensures that community members comprehend the mechanisms of infection and the critical behaviors or activities required to prevent transmission, lessen disease severity, and prevent fatalities. Community involvement is paramount in preventing and controlling Dengue, emphasizing the collaborative efforts needed to combat this health threat effectively.

3. On the significant differences on the perceived impact of the CHN programs and activities in terms of the respondents' demographic profile.

In terms of Age. It reveals that no significant difference existed in the perceived impact of the CHN programs and activities when classified according to their ages. This means that whatever the age bracket of the respondents is, their perceived impact on them is similar.

In terms of Gender. Male and female respondents' perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities does not vary or is the same. This similarity in the perceptions of males and females concerning the CHN programs and activities might be attributed to the

fact that the programs and activities provided by the CHN apply to both males and females. With this result, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities, when grouped according to the respondents' gender, was therefore accepted.

In terms of Educational Background. When grouped according to their educational background, no significant difference existed between the respondents' perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities. This means respondents with different educational backgrounds have a similar perceived impact on CHN programs and activities.

In terms of Family Income. Reveals a significant difference in the perceived impact of the CHN programs and activities when grouped according to their family income. This means that the perceived impact of the respondents with a higher income compared to the lower ones is contradictory.

In terms of Family Structure. Reveals no significant difference. The perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities does not vary or is the same when they are grouped according to family structure. This similarity in the respondents' perceptions with respect to the CHN programs and activities might be attributed to the fact that whatever programs and activities provided by the CHN are applicable to the family structure of the respondents.

In terms of Family Head. It reveals no significant difference. The perceived impact on the CHN programs and activities does not vary or is the same when grouped according to the family head. This similarity in the respondents' perceptions concerning the CHN programs and activities might be attributed to the fact that whatever the programs and activities provided by the CHN applies to whoever is the family head of the respondents.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the respondents' perceived impact on the different CHN programs and activities greatly impacted their personal well-being, and such CHN programs and activities have significantly improved their health status.

Recommendations

Pursuant to the conclusion based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Targeted Health Education Initiatives

Given the significant impact observed in health information dissemination, particularly on Dengue fever prevention, it is recommended to continue and even expand targeted health education initiatives on disease prevention and health promotion. These efforts should focus on providing accurate and accessible information to the community members, thereby enhancing their awareness and understanding of health-related issues.

2. Enhanced Clinic Management Services

Since clinic management was perceived to have a great impact on providing easy access to healthcare services, efforts should be made to enhance and optimize clinic

management services. This could involve streamlining administrative processes, improving service delivery mechanisms, and ensuring the availability of essential healthcare resources to meet the needs of the community effectively.

3. Strengthened Basic Nursing Procedures

The observed impact of basic nursing procedures such as Benedicts' test and wound care management highlights the importance of strengthening basic nursing skills among healthcare providers. Continuous training and skill development programs should be organized to ensure that healthcare professionals are proficient in essential nursing procedures, thereby improving the quality of care delivered to the community.

4. Diversification of Health Promotion Activities

While sports activities were perceived to have a great impact on promoting physical well-being and socialization, there is a need to diversify health promotion activities to cater to the diverse needs and preferences of the community. Exploring innovative approaches such as community gardening, cooking classes focusing on nutritious meals, or mental health awareness campaigns could further engage and empower community members to prioritize their health and well-being.

5. Tailored Health Services during Home Visits

Home visits provided an opportunity to deliver additional health services such as vital sign monitoring, child examinations, and education on breastfeeding and family planning. It is recommended to continue incorporating these services into home visit programs, ensuring that community members receive comprehensive and tailored healthcare interventions in the comfort of their homes.

6. Consideration of Socioeconomic Factors

The significant difference observed in the perceived impact of CHN programs and activities based on family income underscores the importance of considering socioeconomic factors in healthcare planning and delivery. Efforts should be made to address disparities in access to healthcare services and health outcomes among different socioeconomic groups, ensuring that all members of the community have equitable access to quality healthcare.

7. Continued Monitoring and Evaluation

To sustain the positive impact of CHN programs and activities, it is essential to establish robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. Regular assessment of program effectiveness, community satisfaction, and health outcomes will provide valuable insights for ongoing program refinement and improvement, ultimately contributing to the long-term health and well-being of the community.

By implementing the recommendations, healthcare providers and policymakers can further strengthen the effectiveness and reach of CHN initiatives, ultimately contributing to improved health outcomes and quality of life for the community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All ethical criteria were considered when conducting this study. The research topics were not sensitive, nor did they put the participants and the institution at risk. Participation was always voluntary. They were invited to participate by explaining the objectives and giving informed consent for the study. After they had expressed their consent and affixed their signature or thumbprint, the questionnaire was explained to

them. The participants participated by either answering the interviewer or reading and writing their answers. They were informed of their right to withdraw at any moment without the need for an explanation. The researchers employed the appropriate measures during the interaction with the participants, in collecting data or responses, and during the analysis of the gathered data. The participants were assured of the confidentiality of their identity and answers; they were also assured that the answered questionnaires could be accessed only by the researchers or the concerned participants. The benefits of the study were also explained as described in the significance of the study. The research conformed with the Holy Name University Ethics Review Board (HNU-ERB) standards. Approval from the HNU-ERB was sought before the data collection. The researchers declared no potential conflicts of interest concerning the research, authorship, and publication of this article.

Recruitment

The participants' recruitment was done during a home visit. It was always emphasized that their participation was always voluntary. During the recruitment, the introduction of the researchers to the participants was made. Likewise, the following was performed during the recruitment: an explanation of the research purpose, why they were the chosen participants, the benefits of joining the study, the data that were expected from them, and an explanation of the questionnaire surveys, which were divided into two parts. The first part was their demographic profile, including age, gender, educational background, family income, family structure, and family head. The second part was the participants' perceived impact on the Community Health Nursing programs and activities. Participants were assured of the confidentiality of their identity, that all their responses were strictly confidential and would be used only according to the purpose of the study, that they could access the results of the study if they wanted to, and that they could withdraw their participation anytime and that their answer will not be considered in the findings of the study if they opted out.

The consent form was given to the participants for their signature upon their agreement to participate in the study. The researchers thoroughly assessed the participant's voluntariness and understanding. All other important details were written in the consent form, which was translated into Cebuano dialect.

After the participants had affirmed their participation in the study, the researchers handed the informed consent form to them for their signature. The parameters of the study were carefully explained to the participants prior to their signing. It was emphasized that the participants can exercise their right to object at any time. Then, after the participants had affixed their signature or thumbmark in the informed consent, the survey questionnaire was given to the participants, who were interviewed for their responses. The survey questionnaire can be answered within 10-15 minutes.

The participants' identities remain confidential throughout the study, and writing their names on the questionnaire is optional. Taking pictures of the questionnaire and answers, as well as the participants themselves, by any means is not allowed. Only the researchers have direct access to the survey results. After the participants answered the questionnaire, they were secured in an envelope and could be accessed only by the

researchers. The invitation to participate in the study was made during a home visit by the researchers. During the home visit, the researchers performed a visual inspection and asked about the participant's condition before recruitment. The researchers discerned not to proceed with the recruitment when the participants were not feeling well.

The researchers will momentarily stop the process when the participants become uncomfortable or tired. The participants were allowed to rest and resume only when willing. No monetary compensation was given to participants for their participation. They were informed that they could withdraw their participation in the study at any given time and for any reason. In such a case, their responses will not be included.

AN ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM TO IMPROVE COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING PROGRAMS AND ACTIVITIES

I. Rationale

In response to the dynamic shifts within the healthcare landscape, particularly in community health, faculty researchers from Holy Name University present a comprehensive proposal to strengthen community health nursing initiatives. The nursing profession faces an ever-fluid set of local and global demands, necessitating a strategic approach to adapt and thrive within this evolving context.

Once solely focused on increasing its workforce, nursing now finds itself navigating a healthcare environment undergoing a profound transformation. The imperative drives this transformation to meet the ever-changing needs of society, particularly in the field of community health nursing.

The proposal acknowledges the imperative for nursing to transcend numerical expansion and position itself strategically within this changing healthcare paradigm. It recognizes that community health nursing plays a pivotal role in addressing the health needs of populations, promoting well-being, and preventing disease within communities.

The proposal addresses the multifaceted challenges facing community health nursing initiatives by aligning with this vision. Through targeted interventions, collaboration, and innovation, researchers aim to enhance community health nursing programs' effectiveness, reach, and impact.

A comprehensive plan is presented below that encompasses vital objectives, strategies, and program components. The proposal aims to empower nursing professionals, optimize healthcare delivery, and foster collaboration to drive positive change in community health outcomes. Through this proposal, faculty researchers from Holy Name University aspire to contribute to a healthcare system that is responsive, equitable, and resilient, ensuring the well-being of individuals and communities alike.

II. Objectives

- To enhance targeted health education initiatives on disease prevention and health promotion.
- To optimize clinic management services for improved access to healthcare.

- To strengthen basic nursing procedures among healthcare providers.
- To diversify health promotion activities to cater to diverse community needs.
- To provide tailored health services during home visits.
- To address socioeconomic disparities in healthcare access and outcomes.
- To establish robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms for ongoing program refinement.

Program Components

Programs	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES	TIME FRAME	EXPECTED OUTCOMES
Targeted Health Education	- Enhance health education on disease prevention and health promotion.	- Develop culturally sensitive materials. - Conduct workshops and outreach programs.	Within 3 months	Increased community knowledge and awareness of key health topics.
Clinic Management Optimization	- Improve access to healthcare. - Streamline clinic operations. - Ensure availability of supplies and medications.	- Assess clinic infrastructure and service delivery processes. - Implement strategies to improve operations. - Ensure supply availability.	Within 6 months	Reduced waiting times, improved patient experience, and efficient clinic operations.
Basic Nursing Procedures	- Strengthen nursing skills - Provide training and skill development. - Establish mentorship programs.	- Organize training workshops and skill development programs. - Provide access to simulation labs. - Establish mentorship programs.	Within 6 months	Enhanced competence among healthcare providers and improved patient care outcomes.
Diversification of Promotion	- Cater to diverse community needs. - Develop innovative initiatives. - Engage community members as	- Collaborate with organizations and schools. - Partner with sports clubs and cultural groups. - Engage community members.	Within 12 months	Increased participation in health promotion activities, tailored to community needs.

	educators and advocates.			
Tailored Health Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide tailored health services during home visits. - Address social determinants of health. - Empower community health workers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expand home visit programs. - Address social determinants of health. - Empower community health workers. 	Within 6-9 months	Improved health outcomes among individuals and families, particularly those with limited access to healthcare facilities.
Socioeconomic Disparities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Address healthcare disparities. - Implement interventions to tackle social determinants. - Advocate for policy changes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct needs assessments. - Implement targeted interventions. - Advocate for policy changes. 	3 months	Reduced healthcare disparities and improved access to healthcare services for underserved populations.
Monitoring and Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. - Assess program effectiveness and impact. - Solicit stakeholder feedback. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop evaluation frameworks. - Collect and analyze data. - Solicit stakeholder feedback. 	Within 3-6 months	Enhanced accountability, improved program effectiveness, and informed decision-making through data-driven insights.

By implementing the proposed Enhancement Program, the researchers aim to further strengthen Community Health Nursing programs and activities, thereby enhancing their capacity to promote health and well-being within the community. Through targeted interventions, collaborative partnerships, and ongoing monitoring and evaluation, the researchers aspire to create a more resilient, equitable, and sustainable healthcare system that empowers individuals and communities to thrive.

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